

Visual Notes from the

MIT Industrial Liaison Program

2023 Conference

“The parade of excellence on display is astounding. Every single one of the students we see at MIT would be an anomaly in other universities.”

“Welcome to the 2023 MIT R&D Conference Vision for Transformative Impact”

This illustrated summary was initiated, drawn on site, edited and designed by Cooked Illustrations during the **Massachusetts Institute of Technology’s Industrial Liaison Program Conference**, taking place in Boston, USA, on the 15th-16th of November 2023.

All writing and content in this book is an interpretation and creative expansion on the ideas and information presented by the original speakers, here named. Where the information from our notes were not enough, we have found external sources to provide further material, here sourced.

We have tried to ensure accuracy in all the content, but we may have committed some mistakes. If you identify any that require a correction, please get in touch.

“At MIT, we realised that we were a puzzle with a missing piece. And that piece is startup companies. Now, we actively promote between MIT-connected startups and industry.”

Dr John Roberts

Executive Director MIT
Corporate Relations (Interim)

To find out more about Cooked Illustrations’ science and research communication work, scan here:

- In situ drawings by Ian Cooke Tapia
- Editorial and digital drawings by Ian Cooke Tapia
- Additional digital drawings by Lowri Bowden

Travel to the conference co-funded by the **Welsh Government** through their membership of the **Industrial Liaison Program**.

And now, some thoughts shared by Dr Sally Kornbluth, President of MIT.

Dr Kornbluth described Artificial Intelligence as:

“an assistive technology that is at its best when collaborating with humans”

Even in an institution like MIT, they run into entrepreneurs developing solutions for problems that are either misunderstood or really not there.

Runaway genius, coming up with a hundred solutions to a single issue, without first having properly and carefully had deep conversations with customers to properly understand the solution.

“No one likes a solution to a problem they haven't articulated.”

As an example, take a case of a hypothetical AI technology that would support doctors in diagnosing patients.

Whereby the AI would listen in on the conversation, then match the patient's description of their symptoms with an ever-growing database of clinically-vetted information as well as other patient descriptions. The AI would then suggest a diagnosis, which the doctor would check. If successful, the combination of human and artificial intelligence would lead to improved health outcomes.

Wisdom

from
the

**Five
Schools**

**Afterwards, five
academics in
leadership roles
shared their thoughts
on various subjects.**

Daniela Rus

Director of the Computer Science and Artificial Intelligence Laboratory

“I imagine a future where robots are so integrated in the fabric of human life that they become as common as smartphones are today.”

Her assessment is that current AI solutions have plenty of technical challenges.

Costs

AI needs huge amounts of data, incurring great computational and environmental costs

Quality of data

How good is the data in the first place? Bad data means bad performance

Black Box System

It is impossible to find out how the system make decision

Dr Rus work involves three interlinked technologies:

Robotics

Machine learning

Artificial Intelligence

To illustrate why this is bad, Rus shared with us research on self-driving vehicle neural networks, the results of which suggest that liquid networks “seem to understand their tasks better than deep networks”. And, by using fewer artificial neurons, they become a lot easier for humans to understand and investigate how they reach certain decisions.

“The stories of research and science that have the capacity to change the world, involve more than one person.”

Nergis Mavalvala

Dean of MIT School of Science

The School of Science is involved in developing collaborative projects with great transformational potential:

“Finding out how flashing lights at particular frequencies can help reduce some Alzheimer symptoms.”

The Climate Models of the Future

“We are Aggressively, opportunistically collaborative.”

“Every student is a chance to develop a sense of global citizenship.”

Hashim Sarkis

Dean of MIT School of Architecture and Planning

In the context of a changing global, national, and regional entrepreneurship landscape, where funding models are being challenged and changed, Schmittlein prompted us to ask:

“Who would pay for ideas when traditional funders of ideas no longer want to?”

In the context of generative artificial intelligence:

“AI will make the higher performers higher, and the lower performers even lower; as the latter will see AI as effort and avoid learning how to use them because they’re unmotivated – maybe in the wrong organisation even.”

David Schmittlein

Dean of MIT Sloan School of Management

On that point, Schmittlein added on their research on wages.

“Higher wages alone do not lead to higher productivity or engagement.”

Something that challenges a simplistic narrative heard in some circles. What Schmittlein pointed at was a much more complex situation, where employee motivation, workplace culture, and incentives could be a lot more effective than financial gains.

“A technology fails to be successful, if its implementation is NOT successful.”

How we perceive and implement any technologies can make a difference in how they are adopted and used to solve problems. Do it badly, and the technology may itself become a barrier to solving the problem it set out to solve.

Agustin Rayo

Dean of MIT
School of Humanities

Rayo invited us to ponder of two issues that are very useful to think about to help us imagine how Artificial Intelligence may fail to be useful:

Surveillance

or how citizens may react to increased breaches of and invasion of their privacy

So-so services

badly implemented technologies that create mediocre services that get in the way of what users want

These, in Rayo's opinion, may prove the real barrier to adoption of AI technologies, curtailing their transformational and emancipatory capabilities.

Lightning Talks

Innovations from MIT alumni that might change the world

Tom Gurski has designed solutions for sanitation, mobility, and medicine and now his focus is on helping electrify the world's car fleets.

According to Gurski, humanity has already passed the year by which we need to stop producing combustion cars to global warming under 1.5C. Truth of the matter is that we simply cannot produce enough Electric Vehicles fast enough. And even if we could, the cost would be too high, commercially and environmentally.

As such, **we have to electrify existing cars.**

“BlueDot Motorworks is the only service that can help us meet carbon neutral targets in the motor industry. We have developed the only universal technology to electrify existing cars, which “any mechanic, anywhere, in about a day.”

“We can turn any vehicle into a plug-in hybrid vehicle.”

Tom Gurski

Founder and
CEO of Blue Dot
Motorworks

Lightning Talks

Innovations from MIT alumni that might change the world

Peter Schmidt is candid during his presentation: the real point of Transcend Air is to fix regional air transportation and force the airlines to fix the rest of the network by doing so.

His talk asks to imagine a world where there are no airports. No airports, no congestion, no lines waiting anywhere. And all this thanks to the take-off and landing technology they are pioneering at Transcend Air.

The Vy 421 so named “Because it is designed to cruise a 421 knots (486mph)” is 3 times faster than helicopters. It will be able to take you from city to city, with less hassle than short haul flights.

“If you can make helicopters fly as fast as jets, you can sell a lot more of them.”

Peter Schmidt

Co-Founder
COO of
Transcend Air

What keeps us busy in an automated age?

Over the last 100 years, technological advancement meant a seasonal cry of the end of work as we know it. The robots will take all the jobs, the pundits would write and denounce with a misplaced Cassandra-like certainty. But the data tells a different story. If all the jobs are disappearing, then, why are we busier than ever before?

According to David Autor the answer is simple: the perpetual invention of new work. Census data from the USA tell us that 60% of jobs sprouted into existence over the last 80 years, injecting fresh variety and depth into our daily grind.

David Autor

Professor of Economics

“We create new variety and new depth to what we do.”

But what sets new work apart from old work?

Expertise

Autor defined it as “domain-specific knowledge essential for achieving valuable objectives.”

As robots in whatever guise they appear in history start affecting job markets, there is growth in the number of lower and higher expertise jobs, while you see fewer jobs in the middle, which are usually blue-collar factory, administrative and clerical jobs.

“The Barbell of Occupational Polarization”

“Many things that we do we didn’t formalise”.

“Why in the middle?”

Both so-called high and low skill tasks have elements of non-routine structures, which have stood in the way of being computerised, making them difficult to automate. On the higher end, “expert” work has been augmented through computerisation, by gaining access to higher levels of knowledge and information; while the “low skilled” work has generally not been augmented in the same fashion. Think of a policy writer having access to the world of information via the Internet, reducing the amount of time going to a library to perform research, versus a skilled janitorial worker who is, overall, using the same technology as fifty years ago.

However, the middle level of skill has undergone automation: call centres, self-checkouts, for example. This middle ground automation has generally pushed workers into the low skill side of the Barbell of Occupational Polarization.

Polanyi's Paradox can help us explain this phenomenon:

“We cannot computerise tasks that we don't explicitly understand.”

Some forms of work can be readily codified and carried out by computers; things that follow well-understood rules and instructions which can be written as software, will be computerised. Middle-income jobs tend to require tasks that are easily automated. As these middle-income jobs become rarer, they push people into the low-skill end of the bar, where wages are low as you have an abundance supply of people who have knowledge or expertise to do this work. This happens even if the lower paid work is sometimes life-and-death situations and require a lot of expertise – say, a first responder role.

We are now in an era where computers can learn autonomously, accomplish tasks we would call creative, as well as do things we really cannot understand. (That Black Box system described before.)

So, what do we get out of all of this?

AI could commodify expertise.

and

AI could make a little expertise go further.

The Handoff Problem

Autor sees an issue whereby an over-reliance on automated systems can degrade our own expertise, making us less capable. To illustrate this point, think of **The Simpsons** episode “**King-Size Homer**”, in which Homer replaces his menial task of pressing the Y key on his computer with a drinking-bird desk toy. If you know the episode, you know that nearly caused a nuclear meltdown.

“If a machine does most of the work, it is very hard to pay attention”

If technology can be understood as something that shortens the distance between intention and action, what happens when an automated system gets in the way? Imagine the times when an automated door system doesn't work, locking you out in the cold, and you have no idea how to fix it yourself. We want to use technology to augment our expertise, to compliment, and not replace – to make people more effective at what they do, not less.

Considering the current narratives about the trajectories of some automation technologies looming on the horizon, Autor's thoughts help us navigate the storms brought in by the latest season of the end of jobs as we know them.

50 Years ago, we said Fusion Energy will be here in fifty years

“The Engineers are here now. So fusion will be in 10 years. This time, for real.”

In his presentation, Michael Short suggested that it was the advances in materials technology that may prove key in the attainment of fusion energy.

But, before we touch on that, and why is Fusion Energy better than Fission Energy?

Michael Short

Professor of Nuclear Science and Engineering

Associate Director, Plasma Science and Fusion Center

The main one being that, if successful, it would produce more energy than it is required to force the nuclei together. But there are other advantages too:

A lot of green energy

as Fusion would not rely on weather.

No Risk of Nuclear Proliferation

unlike fission energy, fusion doesn't employ material which could be used for weaponry.

No risk of a meltdown

the amount of material in a Fusion reactor would be so little, that even if there were a problem the reactor would cool down within seconds and stop itself from reaching meltdown.

Fewer Emissions

the energy reaction itself would only produce Helium, an inert non-toxic gas as an emission. So, other than the carbon cost of construction and running a reactor, the energy output would be much cleaner than anything we currently have.

That's nice, but how do fusion nuclear reactors work?

To over-simplify it: New reactor designs use a ring-shaped tube design, in which electrical currents and magnets create magnetic fields that squeeze plasma. It is this squeeze that increases the temperature of the plasma to millions of degrees, creating the speed required so that when the particles within the plasma collide, they fuse, releasing a lot of energy in the process.

Plasma ring!

Magnets squeeze that plasma, heating it up

Molten salt reactors use molten salts as either fuel or coolant, offering significant performance and safety advantages. However, these salts are highly corrosive to metals, and the materials within the reactor also face damage from radiation. This makes it crucial to explore alternative materials for the entire nuclear energy process.

Short and his team have been studying how molten salts behave under radiation to identify materials and alloys that can perform better under reactor conditions. Their research has uncovered alloys with a “self-healing” mechanism that slows the rate of corrosion, thanks to specific interactions between the elements in these alloys and the molten salts.

To summarise, Short added, “In terms of corrosion, irradiation makes a good alloy better and a bad alloy worse.”

New Definition of Manufacturing

John Hart

Department Head

Professor of
Mechanical
Engineering

Director, Center
for Advanced
Production
Technologies

Director,
Laboratory for
Manufacturing and
Productivity

“If you look around,
you realise that
everything around
us has been
manufactured.”

“For centuries,
manufacturing has
paced the growth of
society.”

Using cars as a proxy for sophisticated systems, Hart argues that in a 100 years, there hasn't been no fundamental change in the way products are designed and how they relate to the complexity of the manufacturing process. Complexity may have increased, but we still make things in broadly the same ways.

Yet, Hart argues that we must create a “new definition of manufacturing”, one that combines technological and production system research and social sciences research. For while you can innovate more efficient, high-tech

systems of manufacturing; without similar innovations in organizational structures or understanding of wider social changes one cannot hope to truly innovate.

One such way MIT is innovating is in teaching. Whereby manufacturing students no longer sit at lecture halls to listen to a professor “point and talk”, but engage with online material before a hands-on practical class where they can ask questions of each other or the professor.

There are many question Hart's research focuses on. From innovations born from the circular economy, to the opportunities available through digitalization, and questions regarding the number of small versus medium and small-sized enterprises. As manufacturing is closely tied to the world's polycrises of climate change, wealth inequality and national security, innovation in manufacturing helps solve these issues

Inviting industry to engage with MIT, Hart and an audience member had a mini discussion regarding manufacturing, whereby innovation and improvements can be discovered, at a very small scale and in agile ways, if we incorporate manufacturing processes early at the design stage.

Technology

+

Social Sciences

=

Manufacturing innovations
and implementations

“The geometry of methane molecules give methane the “dance” that makes it so good at heating the world.”

Desirée Plata

Associate Professor of Civil and Environmental Engineering

Plata is tackling the challenge of reducing methane in the atmosphere, a critical issue because methane is a potent greenhouse gas. Mitigating atmospheric chemicals is notoriously difficult, as emissions come from numerous diffuse sources, many of which are not human-made, making it impossible to simply “turn off” the tap.

Her lab has discovered a promising approach: passing methane through a heated zeolite, a clay-like material with a texture somewhere between baby powder and cat litter. This process converts methane into CO₂ without requiring combustion. While CO₂ is also a greenhouse gas, methane’s impact on global warming is significantly greater, and it is much more dilute in the atmosphere. Removing methane could therefore have a far greater positive effect on slowing climate change.

The solution is scientifically sound, but the next big question is: how can this technology be positioned in the market?

Plata’s work is looking at deploying the technology in ventilation shafts at coal mines and dairy barns, which would have a measurable impact almost immediately.

Carbon credits?

Part of a mitigation market?

“It’s equivalent to taking all the combustion engine vehicles in the entire world off the road—times three.”

How do you deliver the right skills to the right people in the right way – at global scale?

George Westerman is founder of the Global Opportunities Forum, a worldwide community of organisations aligned on a common goal: to create opportunity for all people through workforce learning.

During his lecture, he asked us to think about:

“What happens to jobs when the robots take over?”

“People need help to grow and thrive in their careers.”

Dr George Westerman

Principal Research Scientist, MIT Open Learning

In the context of how work is changing, then these questions help us understand two **false narratives** about career development.

Managers help their people develop their careers

We give people tools to “own” their own career development

When, in reality, what companies should be doing is to help employees develop their own career development plan, creating platforms for them to take ownership of their own development.

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